

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC, THERMAL AND SPECTRA DATA

No.	Complex	Mol. wt.	% Metal	% Sulphur	% Nitrogen	μ_{eff} B. M.	Molar conductance $\text{Ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$	Thermal Analysis % residue found (NiO)	Electronic spectra (nm)	IR spectra (cm^{-1})
1.	2,3-Diphenyl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone Ni(II).2H ₂ O	735 (718.7)	8.02 (8.17)	3.72 (3.69)	8.74 (8.92)	3.03	8	20.95 (20.6)	360 420 445 530 640	3520 2980 1725 1607 1410 750
2.	2-Phenyl-3-(<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl)*-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone Ni(II).2H ₂ O	731 (750.7)	7.56 (7.45)	3.64 (3.73)	8.44 (8.52)	3.2	12	19.2 (19.0)	360 425 450 540 630	3500 3000 1720 1600 1400 750
3.	2-Phenyl-3-(<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone Ni(II).2H ₂ O	762 (778.7)	7.48 (7.53)	3.72 (3.59)	8.31 (8.22)	3.05	10	19.7 (19.4)	350 425 450 540 650	3500 3000 1730 1600 1390 740

*Cl found 8.7 (8.9)

can be at S, N or O (of CO) site. If the bond is established at sulphur, a six-membered ring will be formed. With either N or O as the donor site, the chelate ring will be seven-membered and hence less stable. On the basis of the structure of the ligand, we suggest Ni-S bonding. The stretching vibration of M-S bond was beyond our ir range. We, therefore, suggest that our complexes are diaquo, octahedral complexes where the ligand binds the metal at S and COO groups.

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Chromium(III) Complexes of 2-(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl) Benzoxazole

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HARKINS *et al*¹ first reported copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt (II) and zinc(II) complexes of 2-(2'-pyridyl) benzoxazole. Oxygen bonded complexes of 2-methylbenzoxazole and of benzoxazole with halides of the above metal ions were studied by Duff and Hughes² and by Duff³. Complexes of some alkyl- and hydroxy-alkyl derivatives of benzoxazoles with silver(I)⁴, niobium pentachloride⁵, palladium(II)⁶ and iridium(III)⁷ have also been reported. We herein report some homo and

and hetero-complexes of chromium(III) with 2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl) benzoxazole, HL, (I)

HL (I)

Experimental

2-(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl) benzoxazole⁸ and trichloro tris (thiourea) chromium(III)⁹ were prepared by standard procedures.

[CrL₃]4H₂O : A mixture of 0.8 gm (~0.004 mol) of the ligand in alcohol, 0.8 gm (~0.002 mol) of [Cr(tu)₃Cl₃] in 20 ml alcohol and 5 ml water was refluxed on a steam bath for 5 hrs.

After filtration the volume was reduced to 30 ml and was left overnight in the refrigerator. 2 ml water was added and the mixture again left in the refrigerator for the separation of the unreacted ligand. After filtration the solution was reduced to 15 ml and allowed to crystallise. Finally, the green crystalline compound was collected, washed with little water and stored in a desiccator.

[Cr(L)(dipy)(tu)₂]Cl₃ : To a 1:1 alcoholic solution of 1 gm of [Cr(tu)₃Cl₃], 0.8 gm of dipridyl was added and the solution was refluxed for 4-5 hrs. 0.5 gm of benzoxazole dissolved in alcohol was then added and refluxing continued for about 16 hrs. After filtration the volume was reduced, 6 ml water added and left in the refrigerator for a few hrs. The unreacted ligand was removed, the solution was concentrated under a stream of air and then left in the refrigerator for 2 days. The solution was scratched with 10 ml water and the separated brown crystalline product was collected, washed with acetone and stored in a desiccator.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA AND PROPERTIES OF CHROMIUM (III) CHELATES

Complex	Cr(%)	N(%)	Cl/C (%)	S/H (%)	H ₂ O(%)	Λ_M	$4A_{2g} \rightarrow 4T_{2g}$
[Cr(L) ₃].4H ₂ O green; $\mu = 3.7$ B.M.	6.5 (6.8)	5.8 (5.6)	61.7* (62.0)	3.9* (4.2)	3.9 (4.2)	(a) 95 (c) 3	17.5 kK
[Cr(L)(<i>o</i> -phen)(tu) ₂]Cl ₂ dirty green; $\mu = 3.6$ B. M.	8.0 (7.8)	15.0 (14.7)	11.3 (10.6)	9.2 (9.6)	—	(a) 79 (b) 149	18.1
[Cr(L)(dipy)(tu) ₂]Cl ₂ brown; $\mu = 3.6$ B.M.	8.2 (8.1)	15.0 (15.2)	11.3 (11.0)	9.7 (9.9)	—	(a) 87 (b) 168	18.5
[Cr(L) ₂ (<i>o</i> -phen)]L snuff; $\mu = 3.8$ B. M.	5.7 (6.0)	8.3 (8.1)	—	—	—	(a) 97	19.2

Figures in parentheses indicate calculated values; * carbon and hydrogen; Λ_M in ohms⁻¹cm²mol⁻¹; (a) 0.001 *M* in methanol; (b) 0.0005 *M* in methanol, (c) 0.001 *M* in nitromethane.

[Cr(L)(*o*-phen)(tu)₂]Cl₂: This was prepared by following a procedure similar to that described above.

[Cr(L)₂(*o*-phen)]L: 0.4 gm (~0.0005 mol) of [Cr(L)₃].4H₂O was added to a hot alcoholic solution of 0.1 gm (~0.0005 mol) of *o*-phenanthroline and refluxed for 1 hr. The colour of the solution changed from green to snuff and some crystals started separating out. The mixture was allowed to crystallise in air for a day. The crystals were collected, washed with acetone and stored in a desiccator.

Analyses and physical methods: Chromium was estimated iodometrically after oxidising to Cr(VI) by fusion with Na₂O₂ and NaOH. Chloride and sulphur were estimated gravimetrically as AgCl and BaSO₄ respectively after fusion with Na₂O₂ and Na₂CO₃. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's combustion technique. Carbon and hydrogen determinations as also the ir spectra were run at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy method using CuSO₄. 5H₂O, as the calibrant. Nujol mull electronic spectra were run at R.S.I.C., Madras. Results are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

2(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl) benzooxazole reacts with tris(thiourea) chromium(III) chloride to give a homo-ligand complex [Cr(L)₃]. The complex is solvolyzed in methanol to a 1:1 electrolyte ($\Lambda_M \sim 95$ ohms⁻¹cm²mol⁻¹). In nitromethane, however, the complex is a non-electrolyte ($\Lambda_M \sim 3$ ohms⁻¹cm²mol⁻¹). In view of the solvolytic nature proportionate amount of *o*-phenanthroline was added to a hot alcoholic solution of the homo-complex [Cr(L)₃]. The resulting mixed chelate, [Cr(L)₂(*o*-phen)]L, was identified by chemical analysis and Λ_M value of 97 ohms⁻¹cm²mol⁻¹ in methanol. A reaction of [Cr(tu)₃]Cl₂ first with *o*-phenanthroline/dipyridyl and then with benzooxazole furnished [Cr(L)(*o*-phen/dipy)(tu)₂]Cl₂. Conductance data of [Cr(L)(dipy)(tu)₂]Cl₂ and [Cr(L)(*o*-phen)(tu)₂]Cl₂ in methanol indicate substantial ion-pairing even at 0.001 *M* level.

The electronic spectra of the above complexes exhibit bands at 520-570 nm and around 410 nm. These bands are assigned to $4A_{2g} \rightarrow 4T_{2g}$ and $4A_{2g} \rightarrow 4T_{2g}(F)$ transitions respectively. The first transition gives a measure of 10 *Dq* value. The magnetic moments are those expected for a *d³* system (3.5-3.8 B.M.).

The ir spectrum of the ligand reveals strong and medium bands at 1630 cm⁻¹ and 1410 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C=N and phenolic-OH vibration. In the complexes the C=N stretch is substantially lowered to around 1605 cm⁻¹ while the 1410 cm⁻¹ band is absent. In the mixed ligand complexes characteristic bands due to dipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline are observed^{10,11}.

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Substituted Malonato Chromium(III) Complexes

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TRIS-malonato¹⁻⁴ and methylmalonato⁵ and also isomeric forms of diaquobismalonato^{6,7} and diaquobismethylmalonato⁵ chromium(III) complexes have been prepared by different workers and all these complexes were employed in mechanistic investiga-